

BEHAVIOUR OF CHLORONITROBENZENES WITH HYDRAZINE AND HYDRAZINE DERIVATIVES. PART IV. SOME HALOGENONITRO-PHENYLHYDRAZINES AND THEIR HYDRAZONES

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4-Chloro-2:6-dinitro-, 4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-, 3-chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-, 6-chloro-2:4-dinitro-3-methyl-, 4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl- and 4-chloro-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-phenylhydrazines have been prepared by replacing a halogen atom by hydrazino group and 2-bromo-5-nitro- and 2-iodo-4-nitro-phenylhydrazines have been obtained from the corresponding anilines by diazotisation and subsequent reduction. Some hydrazones have also been prepared.

The present investigation is an extension of the work published in Parts I and II of this series (Joshi and Deorha, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 34; 1952, 29, 46) and includes the preparation of a few more polynitrophenylhydrazines and also of some mononitrophenylhydrazines. Of these, the substituted phenylhydrazines, listed in Table I, have been obtained by the interaction of 1:4-dichloro-2:6-dinitro-(Hartley and Cohen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 868), 1:4-dibromo-2:6-dinitro-(Jackson and Calhane, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 28, 45), 1:3-dichloro-2:4:6-trinitro-(Sudborough and Picton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 591), 6-chloro-1-bromo-2:4-dinitro-3-methyl-(Cohen and Smithels, *ibid.*, 1914, 105, 1509), 1:4-dibromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-(Cohen and Dutt, *ibid.*, 1912, 103, 502), 4-chloro-1-bromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-(Cohen and Smithels, *loc. cit.*) benzenes respectively with hydrazine hydrate or hydrazine acetate. The halogenomononitrophenylhydrazines could not be prepared like the polynitro compounds; 2-bromo-5-nitro- and 2-iodo-4-nitro-phenylhydrazines have been obtained by diazotising the corresponding nitroanilines (2-bromo-5-nitro- and 2-iodo-4-nitro-anilines) and subsequently reducing the product with sodium sulphite in alkaline medium (Fischer, *Ber.*, 1875, 8, 589).

The yields of the substituted polynitrophenylhydrazines by the method described earlier (*loc. cit.*, 1951), vary considerably. They are remarkably poor in case of 4-chloro- and 4-bromo-2:6-dinitrophenylhydrazines, as when the alcoholic solutions of 1:4-dichloro- and 1:4-dibromo-2:6-dinitrobenzenes and hydrazine hydrate are boiled together (even if the proportion of the latter is less), the main products are the hydrazine salts of 6-chloro- and 6-bromo-4-nitro-1-hydroxy-1:2:3-benzotriazoles. The triazole formation, however, is avoided to a small extent if the reaction is allowed to proceed by adding small amounts of dilute hydrazine hydrate solution at a time at about 20°. 1:4-Dibromo- and 4-chloro-1-bromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methylbenzenes also afford the corresponding hydrazines in poor yields, even on prolonged boiling with hydrazine hydrate solution, as the reactivity of bromine in position-1 in these compounds is comparatively slight though little triazoles are formed in their case.

1:3-Dichloro-2:4:6-trinitrobenzene has two labile chlorine atoms, but only one of them is replaced by the hydrazino group when the alcoholic solution of the compound is boiled with the requisite amount of hydrazine hydrate, and 3-chloro-2:4:6-

trinitrophenylhydrazine is formed. The condensation is accompanied with the formation of only a small quantity of the corresponding triazole.

The structure of the hydrazines follows from their methods of preparation. The hydrazones were prepared by the usual methods. They vary in colour from yellow to red. Those from simple carbonyl compounds are often readily soluble in alcohol, while those from aromatic compounds are soluble comparatively less.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Chloro-2:6-dinitrophenylhydrazine.—To a solution of 1:4-dichloro-2:6 dinitrobenzene in absolute alcohol an equivalent quantity of hydrazine hydrate solution was added in small amounts at a time with vigorous shaking, maintaining the temperature at about 20°, and then left overnight. The substituted hydrazine formed was separated from the triazole salt by repeatedly washing with water and then crystallised from an excess of alcohol.

4-Bromo-2:6-dinitrophenylhydrazine was also similarly prepared (Table I). *3-Chloro-2:4:6-trinitro*, *6-chloro-2:4-dinitro-3-methyl*, *4-bromo- and 4-chloro-2:6-dinitro-3-methylphenylhydrazines* were all prepared by the method already described (*loc. cit.*, 1951).

2-Bromo-5-nitrophenylhydrazine.—A solution of 2-bromo-5-nitroaniline (5 g.) in excess HCl (dil.) and cooled to about 0° was treated with sodium nitrite (2 g.), dissolved in water (15 c.c.). The product was filtered and the filtrate was slowly added to a cooled solution of sodium sulphite (14 g.) and sodium hydroxide (1.5 g.). After about 30 minutes it was acidified with HCl (conc.), warmed to about 56° and left overnight. The solid separating was boiled with HCl (conc.) and cooled, when crystals of 2-bromo-5-nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride separated out. The solid on boiling with water and then treating with sodium acetate gave the free phenylhydrazine, which was crystallised from alcohol.

2-Iodo-4-nitrophenylhydrazine was similarly obtained from 2-iodo-4-nitroaniline.

Characteristics of polynitrophenylhydrazines, prepared as above, are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Substituted phenylhydrazines.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Halogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
1. 4-Chloro-2:6-dinitro-	12%	138°	Reddish yellow	C ₆ H ₃ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	Cl, 15.31%	15.25%
2. 4-Bromo-2:6-dinitro-	10	142°	Do	C ₆ H ₃ O ₄ N ₄ Br	Br, 28.71	28.88
3. Chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-	72	176°	Yellow	C ₆ H ₄ O ₆ N ₆ Cl	Cl, 12.47	12.79
4. 6-Chloro-2:4-dinitro-3-methyl-	69	201°	Lemon-yellow	C ₇ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	Cl, 14.23	14.40
5. 4-Bromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-	20	150°	Light orange-red*	C ₇ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Br	Br, 27.64	27.49
6. 4-Chloro-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-	18	153°	Orange-yellow	C ₇ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	Cl, 14.72	14.40
7. 2-Bromo-5-nitro-	72	161°	Yellow	C ₆ H ₆ O ₂ N ₃ Br	Br, 34.26	34.48
8. 2-Iodo-4-nitro-	68	148°	Do	C ₆ H ₆ O ₂ N ₃ I	I, 45.31	45.51

The *phenylhydrazones* were prepared by heating equimolecular quantities of the substituted phenylhydrazines and the carbonyl compounds in alcohol. In case of polynitrophenylhydrazines, a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid had to be added and heating was done for about 5 minutes, while in the case of mononitrophenylhydrazines, heating for about 20 minutes was necessary. These were crystallised from alcohol; for dinitrophenylhydrazones, however, an excess of alcohol had to be used. Characteristics of the hydrazones prepared are shown in the following tables.

TABLE II

Characteristics of 4-chloro- and 4-bromo-2:6-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

Carbonyl compounds.	4-Chloro-				4-Bromo-			
	M.P.	Colour.	Chlorine.		M.P.	Colour.	Bromine.	
			Found.	Calc.			Found	Calc.
1. Formaldehyde	117°	Yellow	14.48%	14.52%	119°	Yellow	27.33%	27.68%
2. Acetaldehyde	108°	Dirty yellow	13.27	13.73	109°	Dirty yellow	26.13	26.40
3. Benzaldehyde	228°	Orange	11.31	11.08	234°	Orange	21.77	21.92
4. Saffrylaldehyde	223°		10.27	10.55	221°	Do	21.24	21.00
5. <i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	238°	Light violet	10.19	10.55	240°	Light violet	20.87	21.00
6. <i>p</i> - do	238°	Orange-red	10.31	10.55	245°	Orange-red	20.84	21.00
7. Anisaldehyde	198°	Red	10.24	10.11	205°	Red	20.09	20.25
8. Cinnamaldehyde	195°	Do	10.07	10.24	209°	Do	20.21	20.45
9. Vanillin	236°	Light violet	9.76	9.68	253°	Light violet	19.30	19.47
10. Heliotropin	240°	Deep red	9.50	9.74	245°	Deep red	19.41	19.57
11. Protocatechuic aldehyde	239°	Dark brown	9.85	10.06	255° (decomp.)	Dark brown	19.99	20.15
12. Acetone	104°	Yellow	13.18	13.02	96°	Yellow	25.15	25.24
13. Methyleneethyl ketone	132°	Do	12.18	12.39	128°	Orange	24.03	24.18
14. Acetophenone	201°	Orange-red	10.02	10.61	210°	Dark orange-red	21.52	21.11
15. <i>p</i> -Methylacetophenone	213°	Crimson-red	9.98	10.19	223°	Crimson-red	20.17	20.36
16. Benzophenone	225°	Red	8.89	8.95	233°	Red	17.92	18.14

TABLE III

Characteristics of 3-chloro-2:4:6-trinitro and of 6-chloro-2:4-dinitro-3-methylphenylhydrazones.

* Carbonyl compounds.	M.P.	3-Chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-				6-Chloro-2:4-dinitro-3-methyl-			
		Colour.	Chlorine.		M.P.	Colour.	Chlorine.		
			Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.	
1.	152°	Yellow	11.97%	12.26%	216°	Yellowish white	13.51%	13.73%	
2.	130°	Orange-yellow	11.33	11.70	120°	Yellow	12.67	13.02	
3.	237°	Yellow	9.34	9.71	241°	Do	10.17	10.61	
4.	285°	Orange-red	8.87	9.30	245°	Lemon yellow	9.94	10.13	
					(decomp.)				
5.	259°	Red	8.88	9.30	284°	Yellow	9.93	10.13	
					(decomp.)				
6.	279°	Do	8.81	9.30	249°	Golden yellow	9.87	10.13	
					(decomp.)				
7.	240°	Orange	8.34	8.98	229°	Yellow	9.25	9.74	
8.	230°	Red	8.87	9.07	194°	Do	9.01	9.85	
9.	248°	Do	8.17	8.63	248°	Light orange-yellow	9.27	9.32	
10.	249°	Red	8.44	8.67	221°	Deep yellow	9.01	9.38	
11.	279°	Do	8.89	9.14	232°	Orange	9.75	9.69	
12.	114°	Yellow	10.93	11.18	111°	Yellow	11.87	12.39	
13.	158°	Reddish yellow	10.33	10.71	103°	Do	11.46	11.81	
14.	198°	Yellow	9.03	9.35	222°	Do	9.97	10.19	
15.	227°	Orange-red	8.89	9.02	216°	Do	9.43	9.79	
16.	227°	Red	7.73	8.04	205°	Do	8.23	8.65	

* The number of the carbonyl compounds corresponds to those in Table II.

TABLE IV

Characteristics of 4-bromo and 4-chloro-2:6-dinitro-3-methylphenylhydrazones.

Carbonyl compounds.	With 4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-				With 4-chloro-2:6-dinitro-3-methyl-				
	M.P.	Colour.	Bromine.		Carbonyl compounds.	M.P.	Colour.	Chlorine.	
			Found.	Calc.				Found.	Calc.
Benzaldehyde	196°	Orange-red	20.84%	21.11%	Benzaldehyde	199°	Orange-red	10.38%	10.61%
Heliotropin	168°	Red	18.47	18.91	Crotonaldehyde	175°	Red	11.41	11.90
Acetone	102°	Orange-yellow	23.79	24.17	Acetone	106°	Yellow	12.04	12.39
Methylethyl ketone	99°	Do	22.92	23.19	Methylethyl ketone	101°	Orange-yellow	11.40	11.81

TABLE V

Characteristics of 2-bromo- and 2-iodo-4-nitrophenylhydrazones.

* Carbonyl compounds.	2-Bromo-5-nitro-				2-Iodo-4-nitro-			
	M.P.	Colour.	Bromine.		M.P.	Colour.	Iodine.	
			Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
1.	103°	Light yellow	32.34%	32.78%	143°	Light yellow	43.11%	43.64%
2.	110°	Deep yellow	30.94	31.01	135°	Dark brown	41.19	41.64
3.	143°	Orange-yellow	24.67	25.00	157°	Yellow	34.15	34.60
4.	188°	Yellow	23.58	23.81	207°	Dark brown	32.76	33.16
5.	183°	Do	23.51	23.81	228°	Yellowish brown	32.89	33.16
6.	185°	Brown	23.69	23.81	258°	Deep red	32.83	33.16
7.	181°	Red	22.54	22.86	130°	Orange-yellow	31.67	31.99
8.	171°	Deep orange red	22.88	23.12	131°	Orange-red	31.79	32.24
9.	203°	Bright fawn	21.53	21.86	187°	Yellow	30.47	30.75
10.	230°	Orange-yellow	21.79	21.98	208°	Deep yellow	30.71	30.90
11.	234°	Reddish brown	22.54	22.73	242°	Red	31.52	31.83
12.	92°	Yellow	29.10	29.41	112°	Bright yellow	39.64	39.81
13.	75°	Yellowish brown	27.64	27.97	100°	Yellow	37.71	38.15
14.	110°	Yellow	23.72	23.95				
15.	141°	Light orange-yellow	22.73	22.99				
16.	145°	Orange-yellow	19.97	20.20				

* The number of the carbonyl compounds corresponds to those listed in Table II.

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